

Polarographic Studies on the Effect of Some Ionic and Non-ionic Surfactants on the Kinetics of Irreversible Electrode Processes of Arylazopyrimidine and Arylazopyrazole

WAHID U. MALIK* and RAJBEV JAIN

Department of Chemistry, University of Roorkee, Roorkee-247 672

Manuscript received 27 July 1981, revised 19 March 1982, accepted 1 May 1982

Polarographic behaviour of 2-amino-4,6-dimethyl-5-arylazopyrimidine and N'-phenyl-3,5-dimethyl-4-phenylazopyrazole has been studied in 0.1 M KCl in presence of some ionic and non-ionic surfactants. The effect of an increase in surfactant concentration, beyond the concentration just sufficient to eliminate the maxima, on the kinetic parameters of irreversible reduction of arylazopyrimidine and arylazopyrazole has been investigated.

A survey of literature reveals that work on the effect of surfactants on the reaction kinetics of heterocycles at DME is surprisingly scarce^{1,2}. Pyrimidines and pyrazoles are of great medicinal and biological importance and a knowledge of the effect of surfactants on their redox behaviour at the solution-mercury interface may prove very useful from the physiological point of view³. As surfactants are used as emulsifiers in drugs, the effect of the surfactants on redox behaviour of these compounds is of immense importance. With this aim in view the present study covering totally irreversible electrode processes of 2-amino-4,6-dimethyl-5-arylazopyrimidine (A) and N'-phenyl-3,5-dimethyl-4-arylazopyrazole (B) was undertaken.

Experimental

Arylazopyrimidine (A) and arylazopyrazole (B) were synthesized by the method reported from this laboratory^{4,5}. Stock solutions (1.0×10^{-3} M) of compound A and B were prepared in methanol (AnalaR). The buffer used was Britton-Robinson buffers in the pH range 2.0-12.0. All the surfactants used were of high purity and their aqueous solutions were employed.

Polarograms were recorded on a Cambridge pen recording polarograph. The capillary characteristic was $2.040 \text{ mg}^{2/3} \text{ sec}^{-1/3}$. SCE was used as the reference electrode. For recording polarograms 1.0 ml of stock solution (1.0×10^{-3} M) of compound A or B, 1.0 ml of 1.0 M KCl, 5.0 ml of buffer and 3.0 ml of water were mixed and a stream of pure

nitrogen gas was passed for about 5 min to ensure complete deaeration. The requisite amount of surfactant was added, keeping the volume constant in each case. The cell was kept in a thermostated water bath ($25 \pm 0.1^\circ$). The number of electrons involved in the reduction process was calculated by millicoulometry method⁶ using CdSO_4 as a reference solution. Ilkovic equation was used to calculate the value of diffusion coefficient ($D_0^{1/2}$). The kinetic parameters (αn and $k^0_{r,n}$) were calculated by Koutecky's treatment⁷.

Results and Discussion

Pyrimidine A and pyrazole B gave single, well defined, irreversible diffusion controlled reduction waves whose $E_{1/2}$ were pH dependent but i_a remained constant throughout the entire pH range. The $E_{1/2}$ was shifted towards negative potential with increase in pH thereby showing that protonation precedes reduction.

A perusal of the slope value of log plots reveals that the irreversible reduction of pyrimidine and pyrazole becomes more irreversible when the surfactant is gradually increased beyond the concentration just sufficient to eliminate the maxima. For both the ionic and the non-ionic surfactants, i_a decreases and $E_{1/2}$ records a negative shift (Tables 1 and 2) as their concentration is increased.

The product αn_s shows a decrease with the increase in surfactant concentration. The polarographic reduction of arylazopyrimidine and arylazopyrazole was found to be two electron reduction and therefore αn_s , the number of electron involved in the rate-determining step can either be 1 or 2. Since the decrease in the αn value is indistinct and at no stage the two consecutive values vary by a factor of 2, the possibility of decrease in value of the product αn_s due to a change in n_s is ruled out. It can thus be safely concluded that it is the α which is decreasing^{8,9}.

* Present address: Kashmir University, Srinagar (J & K).

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF INCREASING CONCENTRATIONS OF IONIC AND NON-IONIC SURFACTANTS ON THE KINETICS OF IRREVERSIBLE ELECTRODE PROCESS OF ARYLAZOPYRIMIDINE AT pH 6.2

Surfactants	(Surfactant) %	$-E_{1/2}$ V	i_d μ A	αn_a	$D_0^{1/2} \times 10^6$ cm^2/sec	$k_{f,h}^0$ cm/sec
Cationic CTAB	1.0×10^{-2}	0.56	1.25	0.62	8.6	1.2×10^{-10}
	1.6×10^{-2}	0.57	1.22	0.60	8.2	8.6×10^{-11}
	2.2×10^{-2}	0.59	1.16	0.57	8.0	6.0×10^{-11}
CPB	1.4×10^{-2}	0.56	1.25	0.64	8.6	1.2×10^{-10}
	2.0×10^{-2}	0.58	1.20	0.62	8.0	7.2×10^{-11}
	2.6×10^{-2}	0.61	1.14	0.60	7.2	2.2×10^{-11}
Anionic SDS	1.2×10^{-2}	0.56	1.25	0.62	8.6	1.2×10^{-10}
	1.6×10^{-2}	0.59	1.18	0.59	7.8	3.2×10^{-11}
	2.0×10^{-2}	0.62	1.10	0.57	7.0	9.4×10^{-12}
SLS	1.2×10^{-2}	0.56	1.25	0.64	8.6	1.4×10^{-10}
	1.6×10^{-2}	0.60	1.08	0.61	7.9	1.2×10^{-11}
	2.0×10^{-2}	0.64	1.04	0.58	7.5	8.4×10^{-12}
Non-ionic Tween-20	2.0×10^{-2}	0.56	1.25	0.62	8.67	1.2×10^{-10}
	2.4×10^{-2}	0.58	1.09	0.60	8.2	3.8×10^{-11}
	2.8×10^{-2}	0.62	1.04	0.57	7.7	8.4×10^{-12}
Triton X-100	2.0×10^{-2}	0.56	1.25	0.64	8.6	1.2×10^{-10}
	2.4×10^{-2}	0.61	1.15	0.62	8.1	3.4×10^{-11}
	2.8×10^{-2}	0.65	1.05	0.60	7.5	8.6×10^{-12}

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF INCREASING CONCENTRATIONS OF IONIC AND NON-IONIC SURFACTANTS ON THE KINETICS OF IRREVERSIBLE ELECTRODE PROCESS OF ARYLAZOPYRAZOLE AT pH 6.2

Surfactants	(Surfactant) %	$-E_{1/2}$ V	i_d μ A	αn_a	$D_0^{1/2} \times 10^6$ cm^2/sec	$k_{f,h}^0$ cm/sec
Cationic CTAB	1.0×10^{-2}	0.62	1.10	0.72	9.2	1.6×10^{-11}
	1.6×10^{-2}	0.63	1.08	0.69	8.8	9.2×10^{-12}
	2.2×10^{-2}	0.64	1.04	0.65	8.2	8.0×10^{-12}
CPB	1.4×10^{-2}	0.62	1.10	0.72	9.2	1.6×10^{-11}
	2.0×10^{-2}	0.63	1.06	0.69	9.0	8.4×10^{-12}
	2.6×10^{-2}	0.65	1.00	0.65	8.4	3.4×10^{-12}
Anionic SDS	1.2×10^{-2}	0.62	1.08	0.70	9.2	1.6×10^{-11}
	1.6×10^{-2}	0.64	1.04	0.68	8.4	5.6×10^{-12}
	2.0×10^{-2}	0.66	1.00	0.65	7.9	1.0×10^{-12}
SLS	1.2×10^{-2}	0.62	1.10	0.72	9.2	1.8×10^{-11}
	1.6×10^{-2}	0.65	1.05	0.70	8.8	3.4×10^{-12}
	2.0×10^{-2}	0.68	1.01	0.68	8.4	9.8×10^{-12}
Non-ionic Tween-20	2.0×10^{-2}	0.62	1.10	0.72	9.2	1.6×10^{-11}
	2.4×10^{-2}	0.66	1.05	0.69	8.9	6.2×10^{-12}
	2.8×10^{-2}	0.70	1.00	0.66	8.4	9.8×10^{-12}
Triton X-100	2.0×10^{-2}	0.62	1.10	0.72	9.2	1.6×10^{-11}
	2.4×10^{-2}	0.66	1.05	0.70	8.7	5.2×10^{-12}
	2.8×10^{-2}	0.70	1.00	0.65	8.2	9.4×10^{-12}

Concentration of surfactant just sufficient to eliminate the maxima.

CTAB—Cetyltrimethylammonium bromide.

CPB—Cetylpyridinium bromide.

SDS—Sodium dodecyl sulphate.

SLS—Sodium lauryl sulphate.

The transfer coefficient, α , signifies the fraction of the applied voltage which favours the cathodic reduction. A decrease in its value implies that transfer of electrons is made increasingly

difficult. In other words, the electrode reaction of arylazopyrazole and arylazopyrimidine is rendered increasingly irreversible as surfactant is increased beyond the concentration just sufficient to eliminate

the maxima. The decrease in the value of $K_{f,h}^0$ (Tables 1 and 2) with increasing surfactant concentration lends support to this conclusion.

References

1. W. U. MALIK, R. N. GOYAL and R. JAIN, *J. Electroanal. Chem.*, 1978, **87**, 129.
2. R. N. GOYAL, R. JAIN and S. TYAGI, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1978, **53**, 1260.
3. B. PILLMAN and A. PULLMAN, "Quantum Biochemistry", John Wiley & Sons, New York, 1963.
4. H. G. GARG and R. A. SHARMA, *J. Med. Chem.*, 1969, **12**, 112.
5. H. G. GARG, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1961, **38**, 850.
6. T. DEVRIS and J. L. KROON, *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1953, **75**, 2484.
7. J. KOUTECKY, *Chem. Listy*, 1953, **47**, 323.
8. S. S. SHARMA, S. K. JHA and M. SINGH, *Z. Naturforsch.*, 1977, **32b**, 416.
9. S. S. SHARMA, S. K. JHA and M. SINGH, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1977, **15A**, 742.